

Automatic Annotation and Modelling of Works in Eighteenth-Century (Music) Theatre

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Introduction

This paper addresses the annotation and modelling of referenced works in eighteenth-century theatre chronicles, using TEI/XML for the semi-structured encoding of the text and RDF, based on performing arts ontologies, for structured data representation. The topic emerges from the FWF-funded project (grant doi: 10.55776/P36729) “GuDiE” (*Gumpenhuber Digital Edition*, 2024–2028, see the project blog, Braquet/Galka/Korol/Leitner/Zechner 2024–) which is conducted collaboratively between the Department of Arts and Musicology and the Department of Digital Humanities at the University of Graz. The “Gumpenhuber chronicles” document the cultural activities of the Viennese court – a center of European social and cultural life – between 1758 and 1763 [US-CAh MSThr 248–248.3 and A-Wn Mus.Hs. 34580a–c]. The Viennese court maintained an extensive network of representation in which the court thea-

tres (*Kärntnertortheater*, *Burgtheater* and the castle theatres Laxenburg and Schönbrunn) played key roles. In this, the chronicles as a historical text create performance data of a unique kind that is useful for interdisciplinary scholarship on eighteenth-century theatre culture. To approach the specific nature of the Gumpenhuber chronicles from a perspective of in-betweenness, a “digital assertive edition” (Vogeler 2019) is being developed. The chronicles will be modelled using TEI/XML to create a critical digital edition. Additionally, a database based on RDF will be extracted directly from the TEI/XML encoding, linking the structured data (which is founded on performing arts ontologies) back to the original textual source. This “assertive” approach involves annotating the source text – an aspect that has been tested using Large Language Models (LLMs) and will be discussed in this paper – as well as the development of a data model that accounts for the specificities of the historical context in which the data was compiled; i.e. exploring ontological questions regarding the work in music theatre.

Approaching the Text: A Critical Edition of Theatre Chronicles

The implementation of digital scholarly editions often presents challenges, such as the considerable manual effort required for annotation. Moreover, existing methodologies need to be adapted to address the often ambiguous character of historical data, including data of works. In the field of theatre studies, data models such as the *Swiss Performing Arts Model* (SPA) implicitly use modern theatrical practices as underlying conventions for their ontologies. Theatrical practices nevertheless evolve as social practices (see Fischer-Lichte 2021, p. 47) that are closely linked to the cultural surroundings of their times. For example, in the middle of the eighteenth century, theatrical professions did not exist in the same way as we perceive them today. In eighteenth-century performative contexts, theatrical actors often fulfilled multiple professional functions within the same theatre, performing equally as singers, dancers, and musicians.

The hybridity of theatrical professions also shaped eighteenth-century conceptions of the “work” in music theatre. In Italian *opera seria*, for instance, a lyrical text (the *libretto*) was set to music by different composers in various locations and performed by diverse casts. The opera librettos written by Pietro Metastasio (1678–1782) were received as autonomous literary works, and read and collected independently of their musical settings. It was not until the late eighteenth century, and more decisively through the institutionalization of musical theatre practices in the long nineteenth century, that published full scores (as *manifestations*) gained prominence as authoritative representations of the music theatre “text”. Before this ontological shift, *works* in music theatre – and their material sources – existed as components of a modular system that could be

reassembled in numerous ways through performances, either in complete or fragmentary form. Theatrical works additionally underwent genre transformations in the process. The works mentioned in the theatre chronicles comprise different theatrical genres such as French and Italian operas (i.e. *opéra comique*, *opera seria*, *opera buffa*), German and French plays, and dance (ballet, pantomime, divertissements). The works in different genres underwent adaptations, translations, and performances and recombinations of their parts, all of which are recorded by the chronicles.

Approaching the Data: Eighteenth-Century Performance Data

The GuDiE-project will model the data contained in the chronicles of Philipp Gumpenhuber using RDF, drawing from relations in existing performing arts ontologies. *FRBRoo* already defines classes such as *work* and *expression*, and *performance* or *performance plan* for individual performances, and the *SPA* model (Draft, see Estermann/Schneeberger 2017) contains domain-specific classes such as *performing arts production*, which enables the incorporation of backstage personnel. While some classes (i.e. *performing arts production*) are applicable to our context of eighteenth-century theatre, others are not. This is particularly important for the specificities of (music) theatrical works described above, which presents the reason why GuDiE perceives the chronicles as both text and data.

Given the fluid and mutable nature of music theatre works in the eighteenth century, we model the mentioned theatrical works not as abstract *works* in the *FRBR/FRBRoo* sense, but rather as *expressions* (*FRBRoo F2 Expression*) to emphasize their determining content. Thus, we decided to model the content of each expression following the approach proposed by Manzanos (2012). He problematizes the inadequateness of existing approaches in library and information studies that deal with historical sources of (music) theatre. Rather than categorizing types of *works* or *expressions*, Manzanos suggests modelling *types of content* as distinct classes (pp. 448–450). We adopt Manzanos' approach by representing performed works – such as ballets and operas – as *expressions* linked to one or more *types of content*. For example, a performed ballet is modelled as an *expression* with the content types *music* and *choreography*, while an opera is modelled as an *expression* with the content types *music* and *text*. This layered modelling enables a more accurate representation of the ontological ambiguous nature of eighteenth-century music theatre.

Combining Text and Data: (Semi-)Automatic Annotation in Digital Scholarly Editions

The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) has the potential to cause substantial shifts in digital scholarly edition practices, especially in handwritten text recognition, annotation, and text analysis. LLMs have already been used for Named Entity Recognition (see e.g. Tudor/Megyesi/Östling 2025, Hiltmann et al. 2025, Greif/Griesshaber/Greif 2025, Xie et al. 2024, Wang et al. 2023), but there is still a necessity to systematically explore the potential of LLMs for the application in digital scholarly editions (see e.g. the recent call for articles “Digital Scholarly Editions in the Age of AI” for a special issue of the *International Journal of Digital Humanities* on the topic (Pierazzo/Fellegi/Palkó 2025)).

To illustrate this possibility, a previous trial conducted within the FWF-funded project *Digital Edition of the Memoirs of Countess Schwerin* (grant doi: 10.55776/P34943), explored the use of LLMs for the annotation of persons and places using TEI/XML as both input and output format. Three models (GPT-4, Claude Sonnet 3.5, and LLaMA) were compared in the tasks of annotating persons and places in a TEI/XML document containing a sample of the normalized French text. Additionally, the “Schwerin” project team tested different prompting strategies (zero-shot and few-shot) and examined potential sources of error (i.e., whether the models altered the text and in what ways). This trial (Galka 2025), along with other studies (see Hiltmann et al. 2025 and Rastinger 2024), already yielded promising results that showed that LLMs could be used to reduce manual annotation work. The results seemed to be transferable to the encoding of the theatre chronicles, given that both the “Schwerin” and the “GuDiE” projects involve TEI/XML-encoded texts and aim, among others, for the annotation of entities such as persons and places. The theatre chronicles differ merely from the sources in the “Schwerin” project in their predominantly tabular structure and require the automatic annotation of additional information such as performance descriptions, dates, referenced works, persons, and places. During the annotation process, a custom *gudie namespace* is used to enhance the encoding and will be mapped to valid TEI/XML using XSLT once all relevant information is encoded. The semantic layer will be primarily embedded in *@ana* attributes, which will serve as the foundation for generating the RDF database.

The primary goal of the semi-automatic annotation process in “GuDiE” was to identify, tag, and link the theatrical expressions of different genres. Performances of different genres were usually combined in one evening. Additionally, ballets aligned with the first performance of an Italian *opera seria* as part of its dramaturgical concept, were usually adapted, exchanged, or omitted in consecutive performances. However, instead of explicitly naming work titles, the chronicles frequently allude to them implicitly, i.e., by naming

only the genre, using abbreviations, roughly paraphrasing, or giving inconsistent titles. The data's implicit nature made reliable identification and linking particularly challenging for the LLM.

To address this challenge, we processed the TEI/XML in three steps. The annotation workflow presented in this paper was initially applied to one volume of the theatre chronicles, using Claude Sonnet 3.7 to perform Named Entity Recognition of expressions, persons, places, and dates. We selected the 1758 volume [US-CAh MSThr 248] as our starting point because its low data complexity and uniform structure provided a stable foundation for testing our method. Since the volume consisted of 33 separate files, token limitations required us to submit the files individually rather than process the entire volume at once.

During the first step, a minimal few-shot prompt that emphasized strict adherence to the existing TEI structure guided the model. To enhance the performance, project members familiar with both the TEI encoding and the material minimally annotated a gold-standard sample covering one file, which figured as a reference for the prompt. After some testing and iterative refinement of this prompt, based on a single file from the volume's total number of 33, we applied the approach to the full set of documents. Here, the model performed reliably for our case, which was crucial given our initial concern about potential content loss. For instance, only 2 of 4,891 `<lb>` tags (0.04%), 3 of 1,003 `<rs>` tags (0.30%), and 4 of 526 `<persName>` elements (0.76%) were lost or incorrectly handled across the 33 files of the 1758 volume. In total, between 93% and 98% of `<corr>`, `<sic>`, and `<choice>` tags were retained, with only 19 losses across 442 instances. These results demonstrate encouraging evidence that the model was able to preserve the complex structure of our TEI/XML source to a substantial extent. Although the stability of repeated runs was not a central focus of this exploration, we observed that the model generally behaved consistently when both input and prompt were kept identical.

The second step of the process involved linking the annotated entities, especially works and persons, to their corresponding identifiers in external indices, manually created by project members. The index of expressions comprises over 1,200 different entries and organizes regularized expression titles, short titles, as well as inconsistently used alternative titles, or title translations (i.e. titles in the French language for plays performed in the German language). The index of persons incorporates ca. 700 entries including performers, singers, dancers, aristocracy, and backstage personnel and serves the documentation of all performative contributors involved. The indices will be made available in accordance with the FAIR principles and stored under a persistent identifier in the long-term repository GAMS (Humanities' Asset Management System, see e.g. Stigler/Steiner 2018), provided in standardized formats, and linked to authority files (e.g., GND and VIAF for the referenced entities). In contrast to the structural preservation of the TEI/XML, the linking displayed more variation across files, with the same person occasionally receiving different iden-

tifiers. This is not unexpected given the ambiguity of the index, where overlapping surnames within family networks often make it complex to determine which individual is being referenced. Thus, it is difficult for the model to resolve these cases in a uniform way. Because personal names recur frequently throughout the volume, these inconsistencies became particularly noticeable during our review of the output. By comparison, the linking of mentioned expressions was more consistent, likely because the expression index is less ambiguous.

To support the manual reviewing process, we used a custom *Python* script to compare each input-output pair and highlight any immediate discrepancies, as well as *Visual Studio Code*'s file-comparison feature for clearer visual review. Throughout the process, several recurring issues emerged. These included irregular whitespace handling, particularly within `<note>` elements, uniform replacement of typographically correct apostrophes, and inconsistent treatment of genre abbreviations (e.g., *Trag.*, *Op. Com.* for *tragédie* and *opéra comique*) and honorifics (i.e., *M.r.*, or *Mad.le*) within `<persName>` tags. Refining the prompt with clearer instructions (i.e., when to exclude specific abbreviations, or how to handle nested structures) helped the annotation output perform as intended. This targeted refinement highlights that, although the model is sensitive to prompt design, only minor intervention from our side was needed to stabilize these aspects and achieve the desired output. Overall, our explorations show that LLMs can assist with TEI/XML texts and entity identification in historical sources. While not exhaustive or conclusive, the trials offered valuable insights for our project, letting the team test workflows and refine prompts, starting with the less complex 1758 volume [US-CAh MSThr 248] to establish a baseline, then progressing to more complex volumes for experimentation.

Conclusion

This paper outlines a methodologically hybrid approach to modelling eighteenth-century theatre chronicles that navigates the space between structured data and complex historical (con-)text. Contextual information on the performances themselves – a prerequisite for high-quality data – is provided in the edition's critical commentary, which is equally encoded in TEI/XML. This contextual information that informs the final data in the database results from a critical enquiry of contextual sources, among them court calendars, theatre almanacs, accounting books, diaries by aristocratic audience members, musical scores, and libretti printed for first performances. By combining TEI/XML encoding with RDF modelling grounded in performing arts ontologies, we aim not merely to transform archival material into both text and data, but to preserve the semantic and historical nuances embedded in its form. Through our trials with LLMs, we explored semi-automatic annotation processes that can potentially reduce repetitive manual effort while keeping the editorial integrity of the digital edition

intact. These explorations indicate that LLMs can support the workflow, though they still require carefully designed prompts and human oversight to handle ambiguities in complex historical data. Looking ahead, we intend to explore more advanced prompting strategies and to refine the integration of LLMs into our workflow. Key challenges include modelling complex and historically contingent data structures and finding compromises that maintain both the ontological integrity of our data and its accessibility to researchers. Ultimately, our approach supports a more nuanced representation of historical music theatre practices (e.g. *pasticcio*) by embracing the fluidity and hybridity that characterized eighteenth-century performance culture.

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